

tional yield trials at seven locations throughout India, performance was encouraging. Overall performance indicates yields 13.7% higher than IR20.

MDU3 is semidwarf with high tillering ability and is nonlodging. It matures in 120-125 d, 5-10 d earlier than IR20, and has high productivity per day. The grain is long and slender with white rice; cooking quality is good.

ACM8 was screened under artificial as well as field conditions for the important pests and diseases (Table 2). It is highly resistant to GM; resistant to brown planthopper (BPH), leaffolder, and blast and moderately resistant to whitebacked planthopper (WBPH) and brown leaf spot. ■

Table 2. Reaction to major insect pests and diseases at Madurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Pest	Score ^a	
	ACM8 (MDU3)	IR20
BPH (screenhouse)	3	7
WBPH (screenhouse)	5	7
Gall midge		
Screenhouse	0	7
Field	0	9
Leaffolder	3	7
Blast (field)		
Leaf	3	3
Neck	3	5
Brown leaf spot (field)	5	3
Sheath rot (field)	3	3

^aBy the Standard evaluation system for rice.

Using rice nurseries to collect thrips for use in screening rice germplasm

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Breeding for resistance to thrips *Stenchaetothrips biformis* (Bagnall) has lagged because of the lack of large pest numbers needed for screening germplasm.

Greenhouse cultures have failed to provide the thousands of thrips needed.

We developed a simple technique to collect thrips directly from rice nurseries. The nurseries are sown every 2 wk during peak thrips incidence.

Pregerminated IR64 seed was sown in 7- × 1-m beds Aug-Oct 1988 in Coimbatore. At 10, 20, and 30 d after sowing (DAS), seedlings were examined under a binocular microscope. Thrips population/seedling was 5-6 adults at 10 DAS, 60-70

nymphs at 20 DAS, and 75-80 adults at 30 DAS. Thrips nymphs were mopped up at 20 DAS by passing a wet palm 4-5 times across seedlings in the nursery and freed by dipping the hand in a pail of water (see figure). We collected 200-250 thrips per sweep.

Water containing thrips collected per 25 sweeps was poured uniformly on 7-d-old seedlings of test cultivars (including resistant Ptb 21 and susceptible TN1) grown in wooden trays (60 × 40 × 10 cm) inside a large water-filled iron tray. Each seedling was infested with 5-6 nymphs.

Alternatively, water containing thrips was poured on 30-d-old TN1 plants kept inside a water-filled tray. Nymphs settled readily on TN1 plants, which were then tapped gently over seedling trays for infestation. Using thrips collected this way, we were able to screen 400 entries for resistance. The technique can be used in areas where dry weather prevails for 3-4 mo. Thrips populations peak with the onset of dry weather; heavy rains wash them away. ■

Pest resistance—other pests

Reaction of rice cultivar Faro 11 to sugarcane cyst nematode *Heterodera sacchari*

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H. sacchari (Luc and Merny) is widespread in sugarcane cropping areas of Nigeria. In many of the mid-belt states of Nigeria, rice and sugarcane are intercropped or relay-cropped. In earlier screening of some rice varieties, all were susceptible to *H. sacchari*. We studied *H. sacchari* pathogenicity on rice.

Ten-liter plastic buckets were filled with soil collected from an *H. sacchari*-endemic field at the Nigerian Sugar Company plantation, Bacita, and planted with rice cultivar Faro 11. Inocula were juveniles emerging from cysts collected earlier from the same field using a

Schematic of procedure for collecting rice thrips from nurseries to use in screening rice germplasm for thrips resistance.

Effect on rice of *H. sacchari* at various inoculum levels. ^a Niger State, Nigeria

Inoculum level (nematodes/plant)	Tiller no.	Panicle exertion (cm)
0	6.55 a	10.50 c
1,000	4.56 c	12.55 ab
5,000	4.25 c	13.28 a
10,000	5.09 b	11.63 bc

^a Mean separation by DMRT.

Fenwick can and incubated in petri dishes. Inocula were applied at 1,000, 5,000, and 10,000/plant. Steam-sterilized soil was the control treatment. The experiment was laid out in a completely randomized block design with four replications.

Both tillering and panicle exertion were affected significantly by increasing levels of *H. sacchari* (see table). Above the 5,000 inoculum level, nematode influence was less pronounced. This may be related to the self-regulatory property of *H. sacchari* populations under limited food supplies: some juveniles die while others undergo sex change into nonparasitic male forms. ■

Stress tolerance—adverse temperature

Promising cold-tolerant and high-yielding rice lines for Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon

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Rice in Cameroon grows over a broad range of climatic conditions, from a dry tropical climate with less than 800 mm rain in the north to a humid tropical climate with more than 2,000 mm rain in the northwest and west. At Ndop Plain (1,200 m above sea level) in the northwest, about 3,000 ha is planted to irrigated rice with a potential for 15,000 ha.

The rice crop is exposed to low temperature (13–20°C) and associated disease problems (sheath rot [ShR] and glume discoloration [G1D]). Low air and water temperatures, low light intensity, high relative humidity, and intermittent strong winds are yield constraints.

Agronomic studies have shown that changing the planting time is an alternative to escape low temperatures during critical late vegetative and early flowering phases. However, the present area is cultivated by more than 6,000 small farmers, with limited ability to adopt this practice.

Varieties that fit a longer range of planting times are needed. IR7167-33-2-3 was released in 1986 to replace Tainan 5. Its medium, bold, and fairly chalky grain type was an improvement over the short, bold, and chalky grains of Tainan 5. IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan 5 yield an average 3.5 and 3.0 t/ha under farmers' management. The need is for suitable high-yielding varieties with long, slender, translucent grain.

Two advanced lines, TOX3344-TOC-3-4 (derived from TOX3117-18-1/ITA212) and TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3

(from ITA212/B2161C-MR-57-1-3-1), have been identified as promising. Their overall performance over 3 yr (1986–88) in on-station trials at Bamunka, Ndop Plain, was good. Grain yields averaged 6.3 and 5.8 t/ha (Table 1). In researcher-managed trials at Dschang (alt. 1,400 m) during 1988, TOX3344-TOC-34 and TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3 yielded 5.5 and 4.6 t/ha, respectively. Highest yields so far were 7.1 t/ha for TOX3344-TOC-34 and 6.3 t/ha for TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3.

TOX3145-T6C-34-2-3 and TOX3344-TOC-3-4 show greater tolerance for low temperature and greater resistance to ShR and G1D (Table 2). Panicle tip degeneration was more severe in IR7167-33-2-3 and Tainan 5; this is believed to cause direct yield losses.

TOX3344-TOC-3-4 and TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3 have long, slender, translucent grains and, when cooked, are flaky, a characteristic preferred by farmers and local consumers. Palatability tests in 1988 placed TOX3344-TOC-3-4 as best in cooking quality and taste. It is a candidate for release for general cultivation at Ndop Plain. ■

Table 1. Characteristics of promising varieties or advanced lines for irrigated conditions at Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon.

Cultivar	Grain type ^a	Plant height (cm)	Growth duration (d)	Yield ^b (t/ha)
TOX3344-TOC-3-4	L/S	90	120	6.3
TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3	L/S	83	120	5.8
IR7167-33-2-3 ^c	M/B	100	110	4.6
Tainan 5 ^c	S/B	95	111	3.8

^a L/S = long and slender, M/B = medium and bold, S/B = short and bold. ^b Yields averaged over 8 on-station trials 1986–88. ^c Currently recommended variety.

Table 2. Reaction of promising varieties or advanced lines to low temperature and associated diseases at Ndop Plain, Northwest Cameroon.

Cultivar	Low temperature ^a		Disease score ^a	
	Visual score 4 WT (0-9)	Panicle tip degeneration 2 WF (%)	ShR	G1D
TOX3344-3-4	3	5	1	1
TOX3145-TOC-34-2-3	3	5	3	3
IR7167-33-2-3 ^b	5	10	3/5	3
Tainan 5 ^b	1	20	3/5	5

^a WT = weeks after transplanting. WF = weeks after flowering. ^b Currently recommended varieties. Scored with the *Standard evaluation system for rice*.